

Recognition of cultural diversity among Chinese learners of Spanish

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Abstract

A series of lectures on key phrases of national and international figures such as Confucius (孔子), Lao-Tse, (老子), Rabindranath Tagore and Albert Einstein, has been an intentional factor to cover a set of objectives such as familiarization with inter-cultural relations, cultural diversity, the lexicon of intercultural communication, the validity for China of Confucius and Lao Tse's thought, but in Spanish; as well as its comparison with other figures of global scope such as Tagore and Einstein. This precedent made it easier to address the diversity of Spanish-speaking countries, along with the national variants of Spanish. This is because several textbooks on teaching Spanish ELE to Chinese speakers place great emphasis on the Spanish variant in Spain when Spain represents only 9% of Spanish speakers in the world. This contradicts the work of the Association of Spanish Language Academies and its 23 national academies, as well as the editions of the *Dictionary of the Spanish Language*, which have been characterized by their broad inclusiveness as a sign of the growing richness of the Spanish language. At the same time, to motivate diverse reflections, we suggest the role of logical reasoning versus rote repetition that commonly ignores the meaning of the text, elaborating and asking questions versus silence for fear of speaking and the sacralized «authority» of the teacher; group work versus solitary consultation of telephones and translator dictionaries; reasoned reading of texts aloud to break stage fright and other participatory procedures.

Keywords: Cultural diversity, Chinese students, Confucius, Lao-Tse, Tagore, Einstein.

Resumen

Un ciclo de conferencias sobre frases claves de figuras nacionales e internacionales como Confucio (孔子), Lao-Tse, (老子), Rabindranath Tagore y Albert Einstein, ha sido un factor intencional para abarcar un conjunto de objetivos como la familiarización con las relaciones interculturales, la diversidad cultural, el léxico de la comunicación intercultural, la vigencia para China del pensamiento de Confucio y Lao Tse, pero en español; así como su comparación con otras figuras de alcance mundial como Tagore y Einstein. Este precedente facilitó abordar la diversidad de países hispanohablantes, junto con las variantes nacionales del español. Lo anterior se debe a que varios libros de texto sobre la enseñanza del español ELE para chinos hablan hacen gran énfasis en la variante del español en España, cuando este representa solo el 9% de los hispanohablantes en el mundo. Esto contradice la labor de la Asociación de Academias de la Lengua Española, y sus 23 Academias nacionales, así como de las ediciones del *Diccionario de la lengua española*, que se han caracterizado por su amplia inclusividad como muestra de la riqueza creciente de la lengua española. Paralelamente, para motivar diversas reflexiones sugerimos el papel del razonamiento lógico frente a la repetición memorística que comúnmente desconoce el significado del texto, elaborar y realizar preguntas frente al silencio por temor a hablar y a la sacralizada «autoridad» del profesor; el trabajo en grupo frente a la consulta en solitario de teléfonos y diccionarios traductores; lectura razonada de los textos en voz alta para romper el miedo escénico y otros procedimientos participativos.

Palabras claves: Diversidad cultural, estudiantes chinos, Confucio, Lao Tse, Tagore, Einstein.

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Introduction

The issue of cultural diversity and its recognition by Chinese students of Spanish is a key aspect, both at the national level, due to the official presence of 56 ethnic groups by the government of the People's Republic of China, and at the international level, due to their labor insertion in some of the Spanish-speaking countries and as a gnoseological resource for the personal life project in terms of respect for the various cultural manifestations in different geographical spaces.

In this sense, it has been possible to give a cycle of lectures to the final year students of the Spanish degree at Hebei International Studies University on key phrases of national and international figures such as Confucius (孔子), Lao-Tse, (老子), Rabindranath Tagore and Albert Einstein. This cycle was an intentional factor to encompass a set of teaching objectives such as familiarization with intercultural relations, cultural diversity, the lexicon of intercultural communication, the relevance for China of the thought of Confucius and Lao Tse, but in Spanish; as well as their comparison with other figures of global scope such as Tagore and Einstein. This cycle facilitated addressing the diversity of Spanish-speaking countries, along with the national variants of Spanish. This is since several textbooks on teaching Spanish ELE to Chinese speakers place great emphasis on the Spanish variant in Spain when Spain represents only 9% of Spanish speakers in the world. This situation manifested in Spanish texts for Chinese students contradicts the work of the Association of Spanish Language Academies and its 23 national academies, as well as the editions of the "Dictionary of the Spanish Language",² which have been characterized by their broad inclusiveness as a sign of the growing richness of the world's second language. At the same time, to motivate diverse reflections, we suggest the role of logical reasoning versus rote repetition that commonly ignores the meaning of the text, elaborating and asking questions versus silence for fear of speaking and the sacralized "authority" of the teacher; group work versus solitary consultation of telephones and translator dictionaries; reasoned reading of texts aloud to break stage fright and other participatory procedures.

About Confucius and his reflections

The well-known thinker Confucius /孔子 or "Master Kong" (551-479 B.C.E.), whose doctrine is called Confucianism, alternated during his life periods in which he worked as a teacher, with other activities during which he was an official of the small state of Lu, in northeastern China, at the time of fragmentation of power under the Zhou dynasty or period of the Warring Kingdoms (770-476 B.C.E.).

The set of selected phrases has been accompanied by comments and reflections to highlight the validity of his thought, such as:

- "They told it to me, and I forgot it; I saw it and I understood it; I did it and I learned it", with the aim of emphasizing the role played by practice for the development of knowledge, independently of readings and theories on certain issues. In the case of the Spanish language, its practice is extremely important; that is, listening, understanding, and speaking fluently. This situation is not solved by the textbook alone, but by the teacher's creativity, which should not be tied to the textbook. Similarly, when students are crowded in a classroom (50, 60 or more) it is unlikely that they will all be able to repeat words and texts, since, according to the international trend, language groups should have a maximum of 15 students to achieve true familiarization with the language. In this context, practice and its correction during speech are decisive for the proper use of the language.

² *Op. cit.*: 2014.

- "The wise man seeks what he wants in himself; the common man seeks it in others" is a theme associated with the will to be and to do, and self-knowledge. In conjunction, this idea is linked to free thinking and non-dependence on others to exercise intellectual freedom; that is, to think for oneself. It also represents for students the opportunity to break the stage fright or shyness of speaking out loud when the teacher requests it. Thus, overcoming shyness involves a great effort for many Chinese students of Spanish and such a situation must be solved by each student according to his or her interest and dedication, as well as by the teacher with participatory methods.
- "He who masters his anger masters his worst enemy" represents a significant psychological resource of self-control in the face of problems, adversities, and other unfavorable situations; in other words, he who allows himself to be dominated by anger is already lost in the face of adverse situations. This is a key idea with full validity for the professional life of any student in relation to himself and to others. It represents a significant precedent for the problems he must take on in his professional life.
- "Demand a lot from yourself and expect little from others. That way you will save yourself unpleasantness". This reflection is a hymn to perseverance, sacrifice and other moral values that enhance people as part of their life project. The positive or negative influence of the group also plays an important role here. If the group is formed by disconnected and highly individualized people, the group loses its group sense and the demand depends on each one; but if the group operates collectively in the distribution of tasks, activities and in the permanent checking of individual results, the demand should increase and even the group itself should move from one year to another of the university career. The issue does not lie in the fact that part of the group members sit with their backs to the professor, due to overcrowding in the classroom, but that this position neutralizes their attention, where they only hear, but do not see the information projected on the power point and disregard the lecture or consult their respective phones and tablets, and do not attend or understand what the lecturer is trying to say.
- "Choose a job you like, and you will never have to work a day in your life". This phrase can have different interpretations, but it highlights the role of the love of work as an attitude towards working life, especially for young students who have not yet started in these activities or those who, in parallel to their studies, perform other work tasks in their available time. The phrase also contradicts the "task" of working where it is necessary for others and not for the one who performs it, which also creates problems of unsuitability or rejection of one's own work because of impositions and not of personal vocation. This issue has been studied and presented by students in their respective theses, since the variant they receive of Spanish through the texts does not work if instead of going to work in Spain they are sent to Argentina, Bolivia, or Colombia, for example.
- "Learning without thinking is useless. Thinking without learning is dangerous". This statement as a play on words between learning and thinking is also an epistemic resource for learning to think, since it is not possible to learn without thinking during the very process of incorporating knowledge; and on the contrary, only the exercise of thinking without assuming some kind of learning is "dangerous", which can be equivalent to absurdity due to the waste of time. This issue is also related to classroom behavior such as lying down to sleep or rest during a lecture, consulting telephones in class to take calls, opening a food package or a beverage container (tea, soft drink, juice) and tasting food during classes or lectures; in short, dispersing attention in a language other than one's own that requires all possible attention, which also implies or can be interpreted as disrespect for the teacher and the institution where he/she studies.

- "The highest type of man is he who works before he speaks and professes only what he practices". This idea is linked in another way with the first sentence and with another well-known in Spanish as: "hacer es la mejor manera de decir / doing is the best way to tell ", where it again highlights the role of practice as a guide to conduct, together with the congruence between thought and action.
- "If you already know what you have to do and you don't do it, then you are worse off than before". This is also a moral call to duty; another life lesson for university students who repeatedly spend more time playing games on electronic devices than studying systematically, both individually and collectively. The very experience of online classes has witnessed this process, when on repeated occasions they do not activate the cameras to be identified by the professor or simply do not respond to a question they are asked, although they know very well that this is part of their evaluation and even of their attendance to classes.
- "The superior man always thinks of virtue; the vulgar man thinks of comfort". In the present case the notion of virtue is shown to be equivalent to certain values such as sacrifice, work, constancy; while the idea of comfort can be equivalent to in-between-ness, laziness, rest, and inactivity. Another call to be better for the society of his time and, obviously, of other times.
- "When the goal seems difficult, don't change your goal; look for a new path". This is another key phrase for many students facing their respective course work and graduation dissertations when they have difficulties in accessing sources or are not properly prepared in the methods and techniques of scientific research. The point is not to change the objective, but to look for alternatives to provide effective solutions to the problems that arise in any work process. The core of the idea is not to give up but to give free rein to creativity. The individual work of the student is attended by the tutor or scientific director of the work, but the tutor does not substitute the student; on the contrary, when one must attend to a set of course or degree works, a system of consultations is programmed to solve doubts, discuss problems, orient sources, improve the writing, but the responsibility to finish in the foreseen time is of the student.
- "It doesn't matter how slow you go as long as you don't stop". This is another call for perseverance and perseverance. Not everyone marches at the same pace or speed, the important thing in this case is to keep going. This idea can also be linked to cultural diversity and the differences between urban and rural cultures. Many aboriginal communities have a different notion of time where reflection and silence are part of their sense of belonging, while other expressions are rich in hustle and bustle and loud talking. Something similar happens with the notion of time in the dynamics of cities and their great distances, in contrast to many rural areas where the desert, the steppe or the mountain provide another sense of time for those who live in these places.
- "Do not try to put out a fire with fire, nor remedy a flood with water". Although at first glance it may be interpreted as a warning against absurd decisions, it cannot be forgotten that on countless occasions human beings have been characterized by hitting themselves more than once with the same stone or by repeating mistakes that influence the lives of others and endanger the very existence of the species and the world. At present, there are several political decisions that insist on putting out fires with fire, such as the arms race and war conflicts; and pouring water on floods, such as the great contrast between food opulence and hunger; the concentration of financial resources in a select minority group and hundreds of millions in extreme poverty. So, the Confucian idea is very healthy and valid.

- "Study the past if you want to predict the future". In the face of repeated messages of attending only to the here and now, or of the imagined "end of history,"³ this idea underscores the role of historical consciousness as a fundamental resource for foreseeing the future. But studying the past is also a complex and ongoing process, as the world is full of "official histories" that only synthesize and emphasize the interests of various power groups, while many local histories remain silent or have been silenced. This also relates to the interpretation and validation of the past as a resource of accurate knowledge to overcome mistakes and envision a possible or desirable future. It is an early way of opposing the trend of "counterfactual history"⁴ that ignores historical facts and reconstructs its discourse not based on the truth about what was, but on what could have been based on the imagination of the authors or on the proposal of unprovable hypotheses.

In this sense, the students contributed their impressions on the actuality of Confucius' thought in the light of the 21st century.

About Lao-Tse and his ideas

Also called Lao Tzu, Lao Zi, Laozi, Laotian / 老子 or old master, he is considered one of the most relevant philosophers of Chinese civilization, whose tradition considers that he lived in the 6th century B.C.E., although many modern scholars argue that he may have lived approximately in the 4th century B.C.E., during the referred period of the Warring Kingdoms.

The set of selected phrases was also accompanied by comments and reflections to highlight the validity of his thought, such as:

- "The longest journey begins with the first step." This well-known phrase is an invitation to entrepreneurship symbolized by the journey, something that humanity has done since early hominids left Africa and went to populate very diverse spaces. It is also a rejection of statism, of stillness, since the first step represents the action to continue the journey, however long it may be. Today we discuss sustainable development, human development and other issues that have become part of the UN agenda, many of these criteria mark the route of the journey, but it is not always clear whether the route is based on virtuous entrepreneurship or on a vicious circle that, far from reaching a prosperous future, takes us back to other historical stages already suffered by a part of humanity.
- "Silence is a source of great strength". This is a way of dignifying silence in the face of certain expressions, actions and ideas that do not even deserve a comment. It is thus related to another well-known Spanish phrase: "A palabras necias, oídos sordos / To foolish words, deaf ears". But silence is also an important resource for concentration, reflection, preparation for action, and therein lies its strength. For those who study certain subjects, silence is advisable to better attention, rather than the noise and bustle that can lead to dispersion and not taking advantage of what is being studied.
- "If you do not change direction, you may end up where you started". Personally, this quote from Lao-Tse reminds me of Confucius' earlier quote about accomplishing one's goals. Hence the insight of changing direction, without losing the strategic course, so as not to trigger involutive processes or vicious circles that threaten the person, the family, the country, or humanity. The phrase can also be interpreted as a call against fundamentalism, obstinacy,

³ See Fukuyama, 1994.

⁴ See Evans, 2013.

stubbornness, voluntarism, or extreme caprice, depending on the historical context, and therein lies the hard core of its validity.

- "An ant on the move does more than an ox sleeping" relates to the role of constant work as a human value for continued development. It does not matter if the action is small, what is significant is constancy, perseverance as opposed to idleness, laziness, idleness, apathy, and inertia. This idea is linked to the following sentence.
- "Great deeds are made up of small works", for the selective accumulation of what has been accomplished, as in the case of communal attention to the agricultural process of rice, marks for millennia the performance of agricultural cultures in Asia, which have managed to harvest from flooded rice to rainfed rice, from plains to beautiful terraces to make the most of the variations of the terrain and its heights; along with saltwater rice and its yields.⁵ In other words, the small collective work gives rise to great results.
- "The further you go, the less you know". Now we come across another idea that can be interpreted from the field of cultural diversity, for when the traveler sets out for other unknown latitudes he may encounter other human groups whose languages, cultures, senses of belonging-difference, territories, economies, and other characteristics, may not coincide with his cultural references. This is how Marco Polo (1254-1324) felt when he was able to travel through part of China and India and then narrate everything he remembered from his experiences or what others told him. Regardless of his judgments from his knowledge of Europe, he repeatedly compared, sometimes with amazement, other totally foreign cultural expressions.⁶ This phrase is also linked to the following.
- "He who judges everything will find life difficult" if he fails to know in depth the field about which he gives his opinion. The idea can be interpreted as an invitation to know as much as possible and at the same time a critical allusion to the prejudice of judging without knowing. This idea fits like a glove to that type of superficial press that provides half-baked information and judges without sufficient evidence or data, not to mention the other press dependent on the big transnationals specialized in creating false information in the form of supposed "news" and judging a priori what suits the dominant political interests.⁷
- "For the mind that is still, the whole universe surrenders". This is an open invitation to the exercise of the intellect and a criticism of mental passivity, for the human being thus loses the possibility of knowing all that his brief life cycle can allow him. Thus, the universe and its secrets cease to be a field of interest for ignorant people; but I am not referring to the universe in the cosmic sense, but to the universe of knowledge, to the potential capacity of humans to accumulate knowledge and transmit know-how to new generations; in other words, the gnoseological patrimony as an accumulative value of multiple generations.
- "If you correct your mind, the rest of your life will be harmonized". With this idea he emphasizes the decisive role of human behavior as a guide for the rest of your life activities. If you are a person with an organized attitude in your personal, student or work life, you may have more opportunities than another person who is dispersed, disorganized, incoherent with himself and with others to lead a full life. This is related to family and social life since personal behavior also conditions family affection or disaffection and acceptance or not in social life.

⁵ See Guanache, 2021: 57-58.

⁶ See Guanache, 2020a.

⁷ See Chomsky: 2019.

- If you give fish to a hungry man, you nourish him for a day. If you teach him to fish, you nourish him for a lifetime". This phrase marks in a direct way the meaning of lasting and responsible solidarity. One day's help is not the same as the possibility of assimilating a technology to achieve independent performance. It is not the same thing to donate support to a person or a country to create a parasite consumer of what is donated and thus perpetuate dependence like a hungry bird with its mouth always open, as it is to transfer technology to ensure sustainable self-sufficiency in any field. This idea has an indisputable transcendence and topicality.
- "To know that one does not know, that is humility. To think that one knows what one does not know, that is sickness". This is a theme, although reiterated, no less important, since it constitutes a warning about the moral value of humility, since the individual human being cannot encompass all the knowledge accumulated by multiple generations in many cultural and linguistic contexts; hence the false erudition of those who pretend to know about what they do not know is catalogued as "illness". In another way, the Cuban José Martí (1853-1895) testifies in his time in the essay "Our America" (1891) when he states: "The vein villager believes that the whole world is his village [...] What is left of the village in America must wake up. These are not times to go to bed with a handkerchief on your head, but with [...] the weapons of judgment, which defeat the others. Trenches of ideas are worth more than trenches of stone".⁸ In other words, to develop ideas properly, one must be very clear and discern between what is known and what is unknown.
- "That which for the caterpillar is the end of the world, for the rest of the world is called butterfly". This phrase represents a poetic allusion to metamorphosis and a preview to the relativity of the perception of reality from various perspectives. Although neither the caterpillar nor the butterfly is self-conscious, Lao-Tse has articulated this biological process to provide a profound reflection on the interpretation of reality. This is another field of knowledge that is also linked to cultural diversity because what for some people is considered "normal" is to wrap up warm to resist the low temperatures and eat spicy food according to their customs; for others it is to walk with very few clothes or without them to counteract the heat and humidity of the tropics along with the pleasure of eating fresh fruit and enjoying open spaces. Therefore, the phrase could also be interpreted, from the present, as a sign of respect for cultural diversity as human groups have adapted to dissimilar spaces and not from the world that ends for the caterpillar, but from the one that opens on the wings of the butterfly.
- "Kindness in words creates trust. Kindness in thought creates depth. Kindness in giving creates love. On this occasion the outstanding thinker brings us closer to several profiles of kindness as a moral value in interpersonal relationships: trust between people, depth in thinking and love as giving (i.e. gifts, presents) very common among the Chinese, whether flowers, sweets, banquets, certain objects, provided that they cannot be acquired by the recipient. In this sense, kindness is a key feeling for intercultural dialogue as it implies respect for diversity and no imposition of one cultural reference over another.

At the end of the meeting, the students also asked questions and gave their opinions on the relevance of Lao-Tse's thought in the 21st century.

The ideas of Rabindranath Tagore

The great Hindu poet and philosopher Rabindranath Tagore (1861-1941) was awarded the Literature Nobel Prize in 1913. This award made him the first non-European to win this distinction.

⁸ See Martí, 2005: 31.

The selected phrases, full of poetry, were accompanied by comments and reflections to underline the relevance of his thought, such as:

- "I slept and dreamed that life was joy, I awoke and saw that life was service, I served and saw that service was joy". A life devoted to the service of others as an act of pleasure recalls another great thinker, Mother Teresa of Calcutta (1910-1997), who also won the Nobel Peace Prize in 1979 and India's highest civilian award, the Bharat Ratna, in 1980, for her humanitarian work, among other awards. She uttered the well-known phrase: "He who does not live to serve, does not serve to live". Although Mother Teresa's work focused on the needy, Tagore taught international groups of students, artists, linguists and musicians, a training service to which she devoted all her energies. In this student context it is very important to value the work of the university professor in his educational service, his dedication and devotion, even if the institution of which he is a part also emphasizes its economic interests over the remuneration for the teaching work.
- "I have my own version of optimism. If I can't walk through one door, I'll walk through another or make another door. Something wonderful will come, no matter how dark the present is." To some extent this phrase articulates with those previously expressed by Confucius and Lao-Tse, the former on accomplishing goals through a new path, and the latter on changing direction so as not to return to the starting point, where the path (道 / dao), is key to religious thought, the basis of Taoism. What for Chinese thinkers is the path as a symbol to overcome difficulties, for Tagore is the door as a possible barrier, the important thing is to move forward in the face of any difficulty. In this sense, optimism is hierarchized as a human value of total scope in the face of any feeling of pessimism, disillusionment, despair, or other negative perception of circumstances.
- "Be like the sandalwood, which perfumes the axe of the woodcutter who wounds it". The undoubted poetic charge of this phrase suggests the attitude of overcoming human baseness such as betrayal, envy, defamation, ingratitude, and other negative situations. Tagore's own life was subject to these tensions, since he has been considered a cultural reformer who modernized Bengali art in the face of the severe criticism that until then linked it to classicist forms. The experience gained through his contacts with European society and culture, "he became to all intents and purposes one of the most lucid observers and one of the severest critics of the Europeanization of India."⁹
- "If you cry because you cannot see the sun, tears will not let you see the stars". Again, poetic language imposes itself as a call to overcome pessimism and at the same time to see beyond the immediate. In this sense, the image of the sun manifests itself as the near, the immediate, while the stars can represent the future, the desired, the attainable, even if they are light-years away from the observer. The representation of pessimism for any reason is synthesized in the cry that limits the view of the immensity of the universe. This can have several interpretations, but one of them is linked to the very access to deep knowledge, beyond the immediate, beyond appearance. It is another reason for students not to be satisfied with what a class or lecture can provide, but to create the restlessness to delve into new edges of reality, into new fields of knowledge.
- "Love is the ultimate meaning of all that surrounds us. It is not a simple feeling, it is the truth, it is the joy that is at the origin of all creation". One of his many songs to love, so recurrent in poets and philosophers, make of this emotion something more than a feeling -according to Tagore-, analogous to truth and joy, but the philosopher goes much further and links it to the

⁹ See Mishra, 2014: 327-363.

origin of all creation; that is, nothing less than with one of the cultural traits common to humanity, creativity: "a particular human condition of great scope and very involving for the formation and development of arts, sciences, religions, rituality, sports, inventions, leisure, problem-solving, techniques and other modes of adaptation and transformation of the environment-environment and, at the same time, of the very people of which they are a part."¹⁰ In this way, the love of study as a student attitude can gain space in the face of the literal invasion of video games with very diverse contents, among them those of induced violence and selfish feelings that occupy a part of the free time of many university students.

- "Love is life full, just like a glass of wine". As a complementary idea to the previous phrase, love is now equated with fullness, like a glass of wine. Although in the Chinese cultural context wine may be rejected by Buddhists and Islamicist due to the limitations on the consumption of alcoholic beverages, for years now, non-alcoholic wine has also been produced in various countries as a refreshing drink, so that the simile is valid for various cultures. The essence of this phrase is that love is the key to a life full of pleasure.
- "True friendship is like phosphorescence, it shines better when everything is darkened". This is another simile that identifies friendship with light, especially in difficult situations. Sincere friends prove themselves in the face of difficulties. José Martí also extolled it in his *Versos sencillos*: " Si dicen que del joyero / Tome la joya mejor, / Tomo a un amigo sincero / Y pongo a un lado el amor" [If they say from the jeweler / Take the better jewel, / I take a sincere friend / And put aside love].¹¹ The value of friendship in the face of various forms of selfishness or undeclared xenophobia is also a moral call for many students who are unaware of the richness of cultural diversity in their own country and internationally, especially when they finish their studies and must work in another cultural context, whose Spanish does not necessarily coincide with the regional variants of Spain, but with the national variants of Latin America and the Caribbean.
- "I have lost my little drop of dew, says the flower to the dawn sky, which has lost all its stars". Giving voice to the flower that claims its dewdrop from the dawn sky is a special way of poetically valuing the dynamics of the world and of life. In this way Tagore links the flower with the dawn, two connected symbols. In this sense Cirlot refers:

Different flowers usually have different meanings, but, in the general symbolism of the flower, as in many other cases, we already find two essentially diverse structures: the flower in its essence; the flower in its form. By its nature, it is a symbol of the transience of things, of spring and beauty. The sixth of the Eight Chinese Immortals, [Lan Caihe / 采和], appears in images usually in blue costume and carrying a basket of flowers. It is said that he devoted himself to singing verses alluding to the brevity of existence and the ephemerality of pleasures. The Greeks and Romans, in all their festivities, crowned themselves with flowers. They covered with them the dead that they took to the funeral pyre, and they spread them on the sepulchers (less as an offering than as an analogy). It is, therefore, an opposite symbol, but coinciding with the skeleton that the Egyptians put in their banquets to remember the reality of death and to stimulate the enjoyment of life. Now, by its form, the flower is an image of the "center" and, therefore, an archetypal image of the soul. Celestial flowers are called meteorites and shooting stars in alchemy. The flower, in that discipline, is a symbol of the work (of the sun). According to their color, they modify in a certain sense their meaning and nuance it.¹²

¹⁰ See Guanche, 2020b: 54.

¹¹ See Martí, 2007: 300.

¹² See Cirlot, 1992: 205.

The interpretative polysemy of the flower in different cultures broadens the poetic field that associates it with the presence of a new day.

- "Faith is the bird that sings when the dawn is still dark". This other phrase also alludes to the optimism of foresight, to the certainty of dawn when it is not yet daylight, to the conviction that something better will happen. Unlike certain "professors" who warn or threaten students with a possible failure, the motivational interpretation of this phrase should also be aimed at promoting self-confidence, in the ability of each student to succeed in their exams and achieve good results as a potential guarantee of professional success.
- "If you close the door to all mistakes, the truth will also be left out". The recognition that to err is human implies not only to reflexively assume the mistakes made, both in daily private life and in social relations, not only to try not to repeat them, but also not to hide the truth of the facts. Dragging the false idea of the imagined "perfection" is nothing more than a self-deception and a cultural pressure from outside that departs from the diverse characteristics of each student's personality. There are many components that influence this diversity, from genetic factors: aptitudes, character..., to acquired ones: attitudes, motivations, family, and social influences...; all of which allow the notion of truth to flow freely.
- "Asking questions is proof of thinking". This is a key theme due to the experience gained with Chinese Spanish language learners. Out of respect for the teacher in most encounters they are inhibited from asking questions. My response in that case is half joking and at the same time very serious when I point out: "They understood everything, or they understood absolutely nothing". After that sentence, the raised hands appear and thus the disinhibition begins. In any case, we must insist that "the teacher is not the bearer of the whole truth", but transmits the information he knows supported by arguments, sources, and his criteria, but the presence of different points of view and other criteria can enrich any discussion on a given topic. There are personal experiences of the students that contribute to or contradict the teacher's point of view, and this is not disrespectful, but rather a confirmation that reality is always richer than any state of knowledge. That is why it is extremely important that students know that the teacher must also learn from them in each class and that is due to the presence of doubts and intelligent questions that motivate the teacher for that or another next meeting and thus dispel doubts and develop appropriate answers. In this sense, promoting participation in classes and conferences is part of the motivation that the teacher must generate in students to gain confidence and eliminate stage fright and shyness.

After the lecture the students asked questions about their personal experiences and gave their opinions about the relevance of Tagore's thought in the 21st century.

Various quotes by Albert Einstein

Albert Einstein (1879-1955), a German physicist of Jewish origin, later naturalized Swiss, Austrian, and American, is considered the best-known and most popular Western scientist of the 20th century. He has been very famous also for his famous phrases, such as:

- "When a man sits with a pretty girl for an hour, it seems like a minute. But let him sit on a hot stove for a minute and it will seem more than an hour. That is relativity." On the theory of relativity Einstein gave multiple lectures that served to synthesize both the theory of special relativity, published in 1905, on the physics of the motion of bodies in the absence of gravitational forces, and the theory of general relativity, published in 1915, on gravity replacing Newtonian gravity. The basic conception of the theory of relativity is that the location of physical events, both in time and space, are relative to the state of motion of the observer. On

the other hand, in the cultural sphere, although there are various traits common to mankind, there are also multiple expressions of these traits that mark different ways of doing and transmitting accumulated knowledge, some of which are valid for the bearers of a given culture. This relative point of view, in terms of cultural expressions, neutralizes or denies the criterion of superiority-inferiority of some cultures over others, which leads to respect for cultural diversity at the level of all humanity without exception.

- "If you are looking for different results, don't always do the same thing". This methodological criterion is key to conducting both logical thinking and undertaking research in any field. It constitutes a resource that university students should know, since each problem solved in turn generates new edges, new interstices, new questions that enrich what has been achieved and allow opening other levels of analysis of the problem studied. Therefore, it can be related to the knowledge of intercultural relations and the richness of cultural diversity, among other issues. This sentence is a motivation for the following one.
- "The important thing is not to stop asking questions". In my experience with Chinese students, the formulation of questions is a pending subject. For this reason, it is necessary, during a lecture series like this one, to promote the formulation of questions about any doubt, topic, field of research or work method. Such an attitude implies increasing self-confidence and confidence in the teacher. This contrasts with a certain textbook in Spanish whose note in Chinese¹³ explains that the cultural context (a fundamental aspect for the teaching of any language due to its variants) is an extra reading and not a class content so it should not be analyzed, which neutralizes the possibility or the restlessness to ask questions.
- "Learning is experience, everything else is information". Again, this author emphasizes the role of experience, in one's own practice and in the need to critically discern the quality of the information, which can be very valuable and accurate, or simply false and misrepresentative of scientific truth. Therefore, the student must also exercise the right to doubt and practice, as part of their own learning, the verification of information both personally and in groups, not as an act of distrust in the teacher, but as an investigative exercise that contributes to open each field of knowledge to different sources and points of view until arriving at their own convincing conclusions. This represents a solid basis for a permanent process of deepening.
- "We cannot solve problems by thinking in the same way as when we create them". This other idea constitutes a significant compass for problem solving; another key aspect that the student must face in their respective coursework or thesis. Although it is not always easy to define what a problem is, it can be said that it is a formulation proposed for its resolution. However, solving a problem does not mean having a method or way to solve it. Therefore, before attempting to solve a problem, we must answer the following questions: what are the available data, what are the possible solutions, and what characterizes or should characterize a satisfactory solution? Again, Einstein's reflection calls for research as a method and a type of logical thinking contrary to the very act of its creation. The above can also be related to the broad issue of cultural diversity and its accurate understanding by Chinese students as an attitude towards xenophobic and exclusionary views, which contradicts the broad vision of the Chinese government in formulating the socio-cultural scope of the Belt and Road initiative.

¹³ See Yansheng, Pekín, 2014. For example, on page 4 the editor's note states: «(社会文化常识) 板块中的内容为课外阅读材料, 只提供课外阅读的参考资料, 不是授课内容, 切勿在课堂上讲解分析/ The content of the section (General Social and Cultural Knowledge) is extra reading material and is intended to be used as a reference for extra reading, not as class content, and should not be discussed in class.

- "If you want to understand a person, don't listen to their words, observe their behavior." To some extent this idea reiterates an earlier phrase expressed by Confucius,¹⁴ which validates its transcendence from an ancient philosopher to a contemporary physicist. In this sense, an individual's words may not be congruent with his or her behavior and may turn out to be hypocritical or demagogic. This is also a recurring theme in psychology, which distinguishes the ideal self from the public self in relation to the real self, in order to identify similarities and differences;¹⁵ or cultural anthropology, which establishes characteristics between what the witness thinks of himself and others (through the interview) with respect to what the witness really is (through the observation guide) in order to identify similarities and differences between what the interviewee is and what he says he is.
- "Genius is made of 1% talent and 99% work". This phrase, like any other, can be questioned when the act of work takes up more than 9/10ths of the genius and talent is relegated to only 1%. This point of view calls into question the IQ of many people who try to combine ability and work. If the capable person is also a hard worker, he can obtain important results; but a worker with little ability is not always suited to the complexity of the work he must perform; so that the public intention of this author is to overvalue work over ability. This is an issue with many edges and diverse experience, because if the individual's capacity (abstract thinking, physical strength, precision of movements...) is conducive to another activity that does not coincide with his work, the performance is not optimal either. This is an issue that should motivate questions from students, because if the work and its results are important, the ability to do it is also important.
- "The mind is like a parachute; it only works if you open it". In contrast to the previous point of view, this phrase is also fundamental for overcoming prejudices on multiple cultural and knowledge issues in general, both personally and at the international level. Being open to the recognition of cultural diversity implies assuming the definition proposed by UNESCO:

"Cultural diversity" refers to the multiplicity of ways in which the cultures of groups and societies express themselves. These expressions are transmitted within and between groups and societies.

Cultural diversity is manifested not only in the diverse ways in which the cultural heritage of humankind is expressed, enriched, and transmitted through the variety of cultural expressions, but also through different modes of artistic creation, production, dissemination, distribution, and enjoyment of cultural expressions, whatever the means and technologies used.¹⁶

Similarly, in the case of Chinese learners of Spanish, they should be open to the diversity of national and regional variants of this language, since the tendency of texts in China on the teaching of Spanish emphasizes only one variant of Spanish, which, as we have already seen, represents only 9% of speakers, and not on other national and regional variants, much more comprehensive as in the cases of Argentina, Mexico and the United States of America itself, as obvious examples, where the language of Don Quixote is enriched with multiple lexical funds from the native peoples of America, Africa and other immigrant languages of Europe and Asia.¹⁷

¹⁴ See "The highest type of man is he who works before he speaks and professes only what he practices", p. 4.

¹⁵ See Galán, 2020.

¹⁶ See UNESCO, 2005.

¹⁷ See Guancho, 2022, and Sanabria, 2022.

- "There is a driving force more powerful than steam, electricity and atomic energy: the will". On this idea it is very important to distinguish that will is not the same as "voluntarism". In the first case it constitutes the aptitude to decide, order and orient one's own conduct towards a certain objective, without renouncing logical reasoning; this property of the psyche is expressed consciously in the human being to carry out something with the intention of achieving a result; however, voluntarism is a category related to philosophical doctrines that place the will as the first of the psychic powers of the human being in front of reason. Such are the cases of the Scottish theologian John Duns Scotus (1266-1308) in the Middle Ages and the well-known German thinker Arthur Schopenhauer (1788-1860), the German sociologist Ferdinand Tönnies (1855-1936) in the 19th century and the followers of this trend in the 20th and 21st centuries. Voluntarism is expressed in forming ideas or making decisions based on what is desirable or pleasant to imagine, rather than based on evidence and rationality; it is a positive type of fallacy or self-decision making that involves responding to an argument or a statement referring to possible negative or positive consequences. Several studies have consistently shown that, in the face of equiprobable random alternatives, humans tend to predict positive outcomes more often than negative outcomes. In this context, Einstein can be interpreted as valuing volition as a behavioral aptitude that must be opposed to voluntarism as a fallacy of thought; that is, as a source of logical errors and failed actions.¹⁸ Thus, the exercise of a well-oriented will can recognize the general values of cultural diversity and the respectful links of intercultural relations to aspire to a culture of peace and survival of the different human expressions at the global level, regardless of the recognition of local or national heritage.

- "We are all very ignorant. What happens is that we are not all ignorant of the same things". This other important idea is also linked, on the one hand, to the relativity of knowledge and what we ignore. While knowledge in humans endures and is transmitted as a characteristic of the species itself for an indeterminate time, at the individual level it is very limited to each of the capacities during the brief life cycle. In that direction, studies on sociocultural anthropology have provided a wide spectrum of knowledge on cultural diversity and intercultural relations that are not commonly part of Spanish books for Chinese students; for example, they are more limited to Spain than to Latin America and the Caribbean; they equate Spain (country) with Latin America (region) that includes twenty countries and seven territorial dependencies, whose territory is 44 times larger than Spain, without counting the 40 million Spanish speakers in the United States. Complementary studies on the cultural characteristics of other peoples should support one of the international projections of China's Belt and Road initiative, in relation to the key ideas of joint construction, such as the community of interests encompassing mutual political trust, economic fusion and cultural inclusiveness. In the projective sense of the initiative, it is stated that, "We should promote the spirit of the Silk Road, encourage exchanges and mutual learning among civilizations, and pay more attention to humanistic cooperation."¹⁹ However, there are still Chinese teachers of Spanish who ignore the contribution of the aboriginal peoples of Latin America and the Caribbean to the enrichment of the national variants of Spanish in the Americas, as well as those who still think repeatedly in their public presentations that Puerto Rico is an independent country (as many would like) and not a dependency of the United States. There are several Spanish books for Chinese that insist on formulating that Spanish is the third world language when since 2014 it is the second, after the Chinese language,²⁰ among other issues that motivate the promotion of research work and the permanent updating of texts.

¹⁸ See *Falacia Ad Consequentiam*, 2022, and Venturini, 2012: 56-72.

¹⁹ See *Portal de la franja y la ruta*, 2023.

²⁰ See *El español se afianza como segunda lengua del mundo, detrás del chino*, 2022.

- "Strength without love is energy spent in vain". With the recurrence of the role of love, as previously pointed out by Lao Tse²¹ and Tagore,²² this feeling acquires full transcendence for various aspects of personal and social human life. Although the term love is widely polysemic, it has been interpreted and expressed in multiple ways by thinkers, artists, writers, and others, according to their experiences, aspirations, and cultural references. In the case of Einstein, as a consistent physicist, he operates with terms from this field and relates it to force (any agent capable of modifying the amount of movement or the shape of materials) and energy (the capacity to do work). Thus, love is essential for any useful performance and the absence of it represents a waste of time and energy. But this feeling also oscillates between an altruistic (collaborative) quality and a selfish (self-centered) vision with various nuances. Because of his status as a scientist and his contributions to knowledge, there should be no doubt about the altruistic vocation of the author of these ideas and their validity.

As in the previous topics addressed, Einstein's phrases were the subject of questions and reflections by the students.

Conclusions

The present lecture series succeeded in motivating the participation in classes of Chinese students in their final year of the bachelor's degree in Spanish language at Hebei International Studies University in the following way:

1. The role of intercultural relations for the performance of their professional activities as future university graduates was valued.
2. The significance of the recognition of cultural diversity, both nationally and internationally, was noted as part of the policy developed by the country in relation to the Reform and opening up, and as part of the global vision of the Belt and Road.
3. Emphasis was placed on the role of the lexicon on intercultural communication to break down stage fright in class and facilitate the formulation of questions aloud.
4. Interpretation in Spanish of the relevance of Confucius and Lao Tse's thought for young Chinese based on a set of key phrases on various current topics.
5. The main ideas of the previous Chinese sages were compared with other figures of world scope such as Tagore and Einstein, which gave rise to coinciding and discrepant criteria for the development of an open discussion.
6. It was possible to counteract the shyness of participating in classes to demystify the strict "respect" for the teacher, whose word is not divine but human, which obviously can generate doubts, clear understanding in the face of unfamiliar terminology and facilitate a constructive dialogue without inhibitions.

²¹ "Kindness in words creates confidence. Kindness in thought creates depth. Kindness in giving creates love."
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²² "Love is the ultimate meaning of all that surrounds us. It is not a simple feeling, it is the truth, it is the joy that is at the origin of all creation."

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